

DEVELOPMENT AND TESTING OF A BUBBLE FOAM GENERATOR FOR DUST SUPPRESSION

¹Pattayeva Z., ²Darkhanova S., ³Abdisamatov S., ⁴Shokirova S.,
⁵Kuchkarova N., ⁶Ochilov M.

¹Almalyk branch of Tashkent state technical university named after Islam Karimov

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Abstract. This article is devoted to testing and analysis of a bubble foam generator for dust suppression. The study is considered to be actual as a reliable design for a high-expansion foam generator has not been created, the capabilities of existing devices have not been studied, and the binding effect of foams with an expansion ratio of over 1000 units in relation to dust has not been studied at all.

Keywords: foam generator, dust suppression, ratio, system, method.

An important problem of modern chemical technology is the removal of dusty air from production premises and its purification in aspiration systems. Significant dust emissions occur at tire factories and rubber products factories, at carbon black factories, in the paint and varnish industry, in the industry of complex mineral fertilizers, feed yeast, etc. [1].

One of the ways to reduce the volume of air to be cleaned is to localize sources of dust emissions in order to prevent the spread of dust in the space of industrial premises. A promising method for localizing dust emissions is the foam method, which ensures their reliable screening [2]. However, the widespread use of this method is hampered by the high cost of foaming liquids, as well as strict restrictions on the moisture content of the foam, which, if used, will come into contact with a source of dust emissions. Therefore, it is relevant to reduce the consumption of foaming agent and reduce the moisture content of the foam, which is associated with a significant increase in the expansion ratio of the foam used. Unfortunately, to date, a reliable design for a high-expansion foam generator has not been created, the capabilities of existing devices have not been studied, and the binding effect of foams with an expansion ratio of over 1000 units in relation to dust has not been studied at all.

Pic. 1. Scheme of a bubbler foam generator: 1-body; 2-elastic tube; 3- nipple; 4-foam float; 5-foam line; 6-air manifold; 7-window for filling foam concentrate.

The Kirov Polytechnic Institute has developed a bubble-type foam generator [3] (Fig. 1), which makes it possible to obtain high and ultra-high expansion foam. The advantage of the proposed design compared to analogues is that changes in the level of liquid in it, as well as fluctuations in air pressure, practically do not affect the stability of foam formation. The generator works as follows. The foaming agent solution is poured into housing 1 through window 7. Under the action of the buoyant force of the liquid, the foam float 4, made in the form of a ring, floats up, while the air collector 6, rigidly connected to the float 4, is immersed in the solution to a given depth. Through nipple 3, air is supplied through elastic tube 2 to manifold 6. When it enters the solution through the hole in the upper base of the collector, foaming occurs on the surface of the liquid. The rum is full of newly formed bubbles, the foam rises up, exits the foam generator through the foam line 5 and is sent to the dust suppression unit. When the amount of liquid in the housing / changes, the float 4 rises or falls. At the same time, the liquid level above the holes of the manifold 6 remains constant. Due to the constancy of this level, the stability of the properties of the resulting foam is maintained throughout the entire operating time of the generator.

A model of an installation with a capacity of 5 liters of foam concentrate was made and the task was set to study its operating modes in order to obtain foam with the greatest possible expansion rate. The diagram of the pilot plant is shown in Fig. 2. Air from blower 3 through the cleaning system 10-12 [4] was supplied to the foam generator 1 under study, installed in a thermostatically controlled water jacket 2. During the bubbling process, air-mechanical foam was formed, the expansion ratio of which was determined by the standard gravimetric method [5]. The air flow was regulated by valves 4 and monitored by rotameter 5. The temperature and air pressure at the inlet to the foam generator were controlled by thermometer 7 and pressure gauge 6. At the outlet of the foam generator, the foam temperature was measured by thermometer 8. Research was carried out using the theory of mathematical planning of experiments [6]. Based on a priori ranking, factors influencing the foaming process were identified: air flow q through one collector hole, diameter to the collector holes, ratio of the total area of the collector holes S to the cross-sectional area of the generator housing S_g , distance l between adjacent holes, static liquid level above the upper base of the manifold. The flow rate d was varied by changing the total air flow through the collector, the S/S_g factor by changing the number of holes. The experiments were carried out at a constant temperature $(20 \pm 0.5)^\circ\text{C}$. At each point the experiment was repeated 3 times. The working solution was a 1% aqueous solution of foaming agent PO-12.

The experimental plan was chosen 1/4 part of a replica of a complete five-factor experiment, i.e. plan 25-2 with generating ratios $X_4 = X_1 X_2$ and $X_5 = X_2 X_3$. Table 1 shows the levels and intervals of variation of factors, table 2 -planning matrix and experimental results. It can be seen that in experiments 5 and 6 very high foam expansion ratios were obtained.

After excluding factor X_4 , as having a relatively weak effect on the process, a regression equation was obtained

$$\beta = 1841 - 484 X_1 + 753 X_2 - 708 X_3 - 287 X_5 \quad (1)$$

or in natural variables

$$\beta = -1971 - 32 \cdot 10^7 q + 753 \cdot 10^4 d_0 - 354 \cdot 10^4 S_c / S_g - 28,7 \cdot 10^3 h_0 \quad (2)$$

Next, using the Box-Wilson method, a steep ascent was undertaken in the direction of the maximum multiplicity. As a result, when $q = 25 \cdot 10^{-7} \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$, $d_0 = 8 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ m}$, $S_c / S_g = 3 \cdot 10^{-4}$ and $h_0 = 16 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ m}$ value reached $B = 9500 \pm 500$.

In order to study the operating modes of the foam generator at a fixed value of its foam productivity and obtain an interpolation formula, an experimental plan was drawn up and the following series of experiments was carried out. Three factors were varied: 4. do and by.

Pic. 2. Diagram of a pilot plant for studying the operating modes of a foam generator: 1-foam generator; 2-water jacket; 3-blower; 4-valve; 5-rotameter; 6-pressure gauge; 7 and 8 thermometers; 9-liquid thermostat; 10 and 12 - settling tanks, filters; 11-desiccant.

Table 1. Values and intervals of their variation

Levels and intervals of variation	Actual values of factors				
	$q(x_1), 10^{-7} \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$	$d_0(x_2), 10^{-4} \text{ m}$	$S_c/S_r(x_3), 10^{-3} \text{ m}$	$t(x_4), 10^{-3} \text{ m}$	$h_0(x_5), 10^{-3} \text{ m}$
Main level	45	6	7	4	20
Variation interval	15	1	2	1	5
Top level	60	7	9	5	25
Lower level	30	5	5	3	15

Table 2. Planning matrix and results of experiments to study the operating modes of the foam concentrate

Experience number	X ₀	X ₁	X ₂	X ₃	X ₄	X ₅	B
1	+	+	+	+	+	+	1306
2	+	-	+	+	-	+	1893
3	+	+	-	+	-	-	350
4	+	-	-	+	+	-	983
5	+	+	+	-	+	-	3040
6	+	-	+	-	-	-	4139
7	+	+	-	-	-	+	734
8	+	-	-	-	+	+	2284
b ₁	1841	-484	753	-708	62	-287	

Pic. 3. Diagram of a laboratory setup for studying the interaction of foam with dust: 1-foam generator; 2-working bunker; 3-vibration dust dispenser; 4-rack; 5-branch; 6 and 7 dampers; 8-clamp screw; 9-dimensional glass; 10-capacity for collecting excess foam.

As a result, for a productivity of $33-10^{-5} \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$, an equation was obtained which in natural $\beta=1195-194x_1+184 x_2-83 x_3+93 x_1x_2$ (3)

variables has the form

$$\beta = 4852 - 57 \cdot 10^7 q - 374 \cdot 10^4 d_0 - 27 \cdot 10^3 h + 7 \cdot 10^{11} q d_0$$
 (4)

Thus, the studies have shown that the proposed foam generator makes it possible to obtain foam with a wide range of expansion ratios. A decrease in air flow rate d and an increase in the diameter of holes d_0 , as well as a decrease in the static liquid level p , contribute to an increase in the foam expansion ratio in the studied region of the factor space.

To evaluate the binding effect of high-expansion foam in relation to dust of various compositions and dispersion, an experiment was carried out, the essence of which was to determine the specific consumption of a foaming agent solution released during the destruction of foam upon contact with dust. The methodology of L.P. Romensky [7], which allows studying the process in dynamics, was adopted as a basis.

A laboratory installation was installed, the diagram of which is shown in Fig. 3. Foam with the desired properties, obtained in bubble foam generator 1, was fed into hopper 2, where it came into contact with dust particles coming from vibrating dispenser 3. When interacting with dust, the foam was destroyed, and the liquid released was drained through a hole in the bottom of the hopper 2 into a measuring cup 9. The supply of foam into the hopper was regulated using damper 6. Before the start of each series of experiments, samples of the foam entering the hopper were taken to determine its expansion ratio. We preliminarily calculated the volume of liquid Q_0 that flowed out of the foam that spontaneously collapsed per unit time. The specific consumption of the foaming agent was determined by the expression:

$$Q_{\text{ж}} = (V_{\text{ж}} - Q_0 t) / m$$
 (5)

where the specific consumption of foam concentrate, m^3/kg ;

V volume of liquid in measuring cup, m^3 ;

Q_0 the volume of liquid flowing out of the foam that spontaneously collapsed per unit time, m^3/s ; T time of one experiment, s ; m sample of dust, kg . Each experiment was repeated at least 5 times, the maximum experimental error was 6%. In table Figure 3 presents the results of experiments in this series. The equivalent diameter of the foam bubbles was in the range of 5-6 mm. As can be seen from the table, the lowest specific consumption of foaming agent occurs when using foam with a multiplicity of 3000.

The minimum value of Q_l for quartz sand fraction $d \leq 80 \times 10^{-6} m$ is 2.1-2.9 times less than the known results [8] obtained with using foams with a multiplicity of up to 300. Thus, to increase the efficiency of the foam method of dust suppression, it is promising to use high-expansion foam obtained in a developed and tested bubble generator. In this case, the optimal expansion ratio of high-expansion foam corresponds to the minimum specific consumption of the foaming agent solution.

Table 3. Dependence of the specific consumption of the foaming agent solution on the dust dispersion and the foam ratio during foam dust suppression

Foam ratio	Specific consumption of solution $Q_l \cdot 10^{-3} m^3/kg$		
	Lime flour fraction $d < 80 \cdot 10^{-6} m$	Quartz sand fraction $d < 80 \cdot 10^{-6} m$	Quartz sand fraction $d < 80 \cdot 10^{-6} m$ $< d < 140 \cdot 10^{-6}$
1100	4.81	-	1.73
1300	2.93	3.43	0.92
2350	1.96	3.56	0.36
3000	1.25	2.13	0.18
4300	1.50	2.61	0.18

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